

MODA for Impurity Diffusion
Simulated in project *AddMorePower*

OVERVIEW of the SIMULATION		
1	USER CASE	<i>The metallization plate made out of copper of power semiconductors plays an important role in the thermal management. During service at elevated temperatures, impurities present in the base materials might redistribute which lead to local variations of the material properties.</i>
2	CHAIN OF MODELS	MODEL 1
		<i>A diffusion model based on chemical potentials for multiple phases. It is coupled to other models, e.g. for mechanics (anisotropic elasticity and crystal plasticity) and for temperature</i>
3	PUBLICATION PEER-REVIEWING THE DATA	<i>This simulation has not been published yet</i>
4	ACCESS CONDITIONS	<i>An enhanced version of DAMASK (https://damask-multiphysics.org) has been used. DAMASK is free and open source software according to AGPL v3.</i>
5	WORKFLOW AND ITS RATIONALE	<i>The aim of this workflow exaple is to demonstrate the capabilities of the model to predict impurity diffusion in polycrystalline materials. Coupling to other fields is no considered to keep the model simple and focus on the novel aspects.</i>

Workflow picture

MODA

Physics-based Model

MODEL 1

Impurity diffusion

1	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE/SYSTEM TO BE SIMULATED	
1.1	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE TO BE SIMULATED	<i>Prediction of impurity diffusion</i>
1.2	MATERIAL	<i>Copper (Oxygen-free high thermal conductivity, OFHC)</i>
1.3	GEOMETRY	<i>Flexible. For a simple test case, use a spherical inclusion in a single crystal with cube orientation. The initial concentration is set to 98%-2% in the inclusion and 100% elsewhere.</i>
1.4	TIME LAPSE	<i>flexible</i>
1.5	MANUFACTURING PROCESS OR IN-SERVICE CONDITIONS	<i>The stress on the sides of the volume element is set to 0.0 MPa. Periodic boundary conditions apply.</i>
1.6	PUBLICATION ON THIS DATA	<i>n/a</i>

2 GENERIC PHYSICS OF THE MODEL EQUATION		
2.0	MODEL TYPE AND NAME	<i>Continuum model/Solid Mechanics.</i>
2.1	MODEL ENTITY	<i>The entities in this material model are finite volumes/grains.</i>
2.2	MODEL PHYSICS/CHEMISTRY EQUATION PE	Physical Equation <i>Diffusion</i> $\dot{c}_m = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{j}_m + f_m, \quad \text{for } m = 1, \dots, N$ <i>with conservation of mass</i> $0 \leq c_m \leq 1, \text{ and } \sum_{m=1}^N c_m = 1.0.$
		Physical Quantities 1. c_m : concentration of component m 2. \mathbf{j}_m : flux 3. f_m : optional source or sink the matrix 4. N: number of components
2.3	MATERIALS RELATIONS	Relation $\mathbf{j}_m = -M_m \nabla \mu_m$ $\mu_m = \frac{\delta \psi}{\delta c_m}$ $\psi = \psi_{\text{hom}} + \psi_{\text{grad}}$ $\psi = \psi(c_m, \nabla c_m)$ $\psi_{\text{grad}} = \kappa (\nabla c_m)^2$
		Physical quantities/descriptors for each MR M_m : atomic mobility μ_m : chemical potential ψ : free energy ψ_{hom} : homogeneous part of the free energy ψ_{grad} : gradient/interfacial part of the free energy κ : gradient coefficient
2.4	SIMULATED INPUT	<i>n/a</i>

3 SOLVER AND COMPUTATIONAL TRANSLATION OF THE SPECIFICATIONS		
3.1	NUMERICAL SOLVER	<i>Finite different solver based on PETSc</i>
3.2	SOFTWARE TOOL	<i>DAMASK (license AGPL v3)</i> https://damask-multiphysics.org https://doi.org/10.1016/j.commat.2018.04.030
3.3	TIME STEP	<i>10s (in total 100 time steps)</i>
3.4	COMPUTATIONAL REPRESENTATION	PHYSICS EQUATION, MATERIAL RELATIONS, MATERIAL <i>n/a</i>
3.5	COMPUTATIONAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS	<i>Periodic boundary conditions apply</i>
3.6	ADDITIONAL SOLVER PARAMETERS	<i>See PETSc manual</i>